

MANAJEMEN SARANA DAN PRASARANA DALAM MENINGKATKAN PRODUKTIVITAS DI SEKOLAH DASAR

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Abstrak

Tujuan penelitian untuk mendeskripsikan manajemen sarana dan prasarana di Sekolah Dasar Islam Terpadu (SDIT) Al-Fityan Kubu Raya. Metode penelitian yang digunakan yaitu metode deskriptif kualitatif. Penelitian dilakukan di SDIT Al-Fityan Kubu Raya dengan subjek penelitian yaitu: kepala sekolah; wakil kepala sekolah bidang kesiswaan dan kurikulum; bendahara; serta staf tata usaha. Teknik pengumpulan data berupa wawancara, observasi, dan studi dokumentasi. Teknik analisis data menggunakan analisis deskriptif. Hasil penelitian menunjukkan bahwa: (1) Kebijakan perencanaan sarana dan prasarana disusun pada awal tahun dengan menganalisis kebutuhan; (2) Kebijakan pengadaan sarana dan prasarana sesuai dengan prosedur yang ada; (3) kebijakan pengorganisasian sarana dan prasarana sesuai dengan keputusan kepala sekolah; dan (4) pemeliharaan sarana dan prasarana cukup akuntabel.

Kata Kunci: manajemen, sarana dan prasarana, produktivitas sekolah.

Abstract

The purpose of the research was to describe the management of facilities and infrastructure at the Al-Fityan Kubu Raya Islamic Elementary School. The research method used descriptive method with a qualitative approach. The research was conducted at SDIT Al-Fityan Kubu Raya with the research subjects: the principal, the vice-principal of the student affairs and curriculum; treasurer; and administrative staff. Data collection techniques used interviews, observation, and documentation. The data analysis technique used descriptive analysis. The results of the research indicate that: (1) The planning policy for facilities and infrastructure are prepared at the beginning of the year by analyzing needs; (2) The policy for the procurement of facilities and infrastructure is in accordance with existing procedures; (3) The policy of organizing facilities and infrastructure in accordance with the decision of the principal; and (4) The maintenance of facilities and infrastructure is sufficiently accountable.

Keywords: management, facilities and infrastructure, school productivity.